

(ΔH°), free energy (ΔG°) and entropy change (ΔS°) for $[\text{Cd}(\text{P. Procaine})]^{2+}$ have been recorded in Tables 2 and 3.

The values of free energy for $[\text{Cd}(\text{P. Procaine})]^{2+}$ shows that free energy for 1 : 1 complex is just double in 20% (v/v) methanol-water mixture than in 20% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture. The lower values of (ΔG°) at higher temperature confirms that the complexes are not stable at higher temperature. The negative values of enthalpy (ΔH°) show that the reaction is exothermic in nature. The negative values of entropy show that formed complex is in more ordered form.

in this study. All solutions were made in double distilled water and overall study has been done in 20% (v/v) methanol-water mixture and 20% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture medium. Triton X-100 (0.005%) was used to suppressed the polarographic maxima. The solution of Cd^{II} [$2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$] in double-distilled water containing 1 M KNO_3 as supporting electrolyte, required amount of solvent and ligand solution were taken in the sample cell. It was deaerated prior to polarographic study, to protect from the atmosphere. The depolariser and ligand (antibiotic) were taken in the definite ratio in binary complexes the concentration of antibiotic was varied in definite ratio.

Table 1. Stability constants for cadmium penicillin procaine salt system in 20% (v/v) methanol-water mixture and 20% v/v ethanol-water mixture

System	Composition of complexes	Stability constant 20% methanol		Stability constant 20% ethanol	
		30°C	40°C	30°C	40°C
$[\text{Cd}(\text{P. Procaine})]^{2+}$	1 : 1	10.1667	6.0737	4.5563	7.8517

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters for cadmium penicillin procaine salt system in 20% (v/v) methanol-water mixture at 30 °C

System	Composition of complexes	Thermodynamic parameters		
		ΔG° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS° JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
$[\text{Cd}(\text{P. Procaine})]^{2+}$	1 : 1	-28.17	-187.22	-0.52

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters for cadmium penicillin procaine salt system in 20% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture at 30 °C

System	Composition of complexes	Thermodynamic parameters		
		ΔG° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS° JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
$[\text{Cd}(\text{P. Procaine})]^{2+}$	1 : 1	-35.24	-242.06	-0.68

Experimental

A model CL357 a polarographic analyzer (from Elico) was coupled with cell for direct current polarographic experiments. The current response and the applied potential were recorded at scan rate 150 mV/min. The current voltage measurements were performed with three electrodes assembly, a dropping mercury electrode as working electrode, calomel as reference and platinum as counter electrode.

Analytical grade (S.d. fine) cadmium acetate was used

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Reference

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